

Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons and Respiratory Toxicity: A Review

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ABSTRACT: Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) are environmental pollutants primarily associated with chronic respiratory illness. Increased epidemiological findings necessitate a concentrated effort to raise awareness regarding the influence of air quality on the prevalence of highlighted PAHs in airborne particles. PAHs have been associated with respiratory problems including asthma, asthma exacerbation, chronic bronchitis, and emphysema. The review gives an insight into the recent PAHs exposure and its toxicity effects on the respiratory system. A literature search across four scientific databases yielded 120 relevant studies, including articles analyzing urinary concentrations of various persistent PAHs and their biomarkers. The study also highlighted the risk posed by PM_{2.5}-PAHs conjugates in causing mutagenesis, carcinogenesis, teratogenesis, disrupting signalling pathways resulting in oxidative stress, acute and/or chronic respiratory morbidity, cognitive impairment, cardiovascular morbidity, and mortality. The study further emphasizes PAHs' and their metabolites' significant toxicity to the respiratory system, inducing AhR/nonAhR interlinked signalling mechanisms that lead to oxidative stress, immune system damage, asthma/COPD, and cancer. In conclusion, the study predominantly indicates positive correlations between PAHs and respiratory toxicity.

KEYWORDS: Biomarkers, Oxidative Stress, PAHs, Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons, Respiratory Morbidity.

INTRODUCTION

The current scenario witnesses a rapid growth in industrialization and urbanization which has drastically led to a significant increase in the upsurge of various pollutants including Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs). [1] PAHs are ubiquitous, persistent toxic xenobiotic chemicals released directly from both natural events like forest fires, and volcanic eruption, as well as anthropogenic activities like incomplete combustion of fossil fuels and industrial processes. PAHs are a prevalent class of environmental pollutants, typically manifest as intricate combinations of more than 300 organic compounds containing multiple aromatic rings. These compounds are noteworthy for their extensive distribution and potential to cause cancer, mutate genes, and induce toxicity. [2–7] PAHs are primarily 2-6 fused aromatic rings found in different configurations. [8–12] Based on source of origin 9 compounds are categorized as 'petrogenic PAHs' (alkylated or oxygenated PAHs arising from oil spills) and 16 priority PAHs are categorized as 'pyrogenic PAHs' (arising from fossil fuel) (Table 1) which are predominate in the atmosphere. [10, 13–15] Although levels of PAHs vary in the environment, some of them, such as the extremely carcinogenic B[a]P, account for only 3% of the emission of 16 priority PAHs. High molecular mass PAHs pose a significant respiratory exposure risk as mutagen and cancer exist in both gaseous and particulate forms. [3, 7, 16–18]

The emergence of PAHs from air pollution is recognized to impact the health of both humans and other organisms, either directly or indirectly. Recent epidemiological studies have provided compelling evidence linking PAHs exposure to respiratory diseases and mortality rates. [19, 20] Exposure to PAHs and their photochemical oxidation product may result in lung cancer development. [21–25] Furthermore, advancements in extraction techniques (solid phase microextraction, solid phase extraction, and liquid-liquid extraction), analytical techniques including GCMSMS, HPLCMSMS, UPLC-MSMS, miniaturized and portable devices (microfluidic technology, electrochemical sensors, surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy), molecular and immunologic assays, and computational modelling have enabled researchers to quantify PAHs levels in various environmental matrices and biological samples with greater accuracy and sensitivity. [26, 27] Moreover, recent molecular and mechanistic studies have elucidated the cellular pathways involved in PAHs-induced respiratory toxicity, paving the way for the development of novel therapeutic

strategies.[20, 28, 29] In recent years, the escalation of anthropogenic activities has notably heightened the release of PAHs into the soil, water, and air, surpassing their respective permissible limits.[30–32] Recent investigations have established that these substances are potential carcinogens.[2, 3, 7, 33] PAHs have been classified into 4 groups namely ‘Group 1 Carcinogenic to humans’, ‘Group 2A Probably carcinogenic to humans’, ‘Group 2B Possibly carcinogenic to humans’, and ‘Group 3 Not classifiable as to its carcinogenicity to humans’ (Table 1).[34, 35] PAHs specifically chrysene- CHR, benzo[a]pyrene- B[a]P, benzo[a]anthracene- B[a]A, and benzo[b]fluoranthene- B[b]F are known as mutagens, teratogens, and carcinogens.[10, 36]

Previous research on PAHs and respiratory toxicity has made significant knowledge, yet several gaps remain including combined mechanistic insights into PAH-induced respiratory effects and precise exposure assessment methods.[37–39] Addressing these gaps will lead to a more comprehensive understanding of PAHs' respiratory toxicity and facilitate a clearer understanding of the mechanisms, biomarkers, epidemiological associations, risk assessment approaches, and intervention strategies. The authors hereby intend to explore the recent trends in identifying the current situation regarding respiratory issues caused by PAHs as well as in establishing the role of PAHs in respiratory illnesses. Limiting the literature search for a specific period provides more precise techniques leading to more accurate detection of PAHs and their metabolite levels in biological systems. The last 5 years duration also identified the current situation regarding respiratory issues caused by PAHs and developed epidemiological evidence of PAHs role in respiratory problems, if any. A literature survey for a specific timeline provides the most up-to-date findings, enhancing the relevance and timeliness of the research and enabling the review to encompass a comprehensive range of recent studies. The present study may also serve as a basis for future research development for providing more accurate interpretations using pre-designed synergistic signalling pathways for effective interventions and innovative strategies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

An observational study was conducted for published articles during the last five years to investigate the relationship between PAHs exposure and progression of respiratory toxicity.

Search Strategy

The literature survey was done using Elsevier- Science Direct, PubMed, Scholar Google, and Springer databases which identify articles recently published in scientific journals *i.e.* MDPI, Nature, SAGE, ScienceDirect, Springer, Wiley, Hindawi, etc. from the year April 2019 - July 2024. The relevant keywords used for the literature were ‘PAHs exposure’, ‘PAHs respiratory health’, ‘PAHs toxicity mechanism’, ‘PAHs metabolism’, ‘PAHs metabolites’, and ‘PAHs exposure effect’. Additionally, standard guidelines representing the nomenclature and classification of PAHs were also included (Table S1).[40, 41]

Inclusion Criteria

Original, full-text research articles, review articles, and clinical studies in the English language were considered for inclusion. The study was included if represented the PAHs exposure effect among healthy subjects and/or provided the mechanism of action of PAHs exposure. Articles representing the relationship between toxic PAHs exposure and lung inflammation, impaired pulmonary functioning, lung cancer, COPD, and acute lower respiratory infection (ALRI) were also included.

Exclusion Criteria

The study excluded those in non-English language OR irrelevant study populations OR unrelated exposures and/or unrelated outcomes OR considered patients with previously reported other risk factors were excluded. Studies were pooled and compiled using the Rayyan portal (Ouzzani *et al.*, 2016).[42]

For the evaluation of PAHs-based respiratory toxicity, the initial search identified 3998 studies from four different databases. From these studies, 3892 articles were withdrawn (328 duplicate articles, 888 irrelevant articles, 1396 excluded by title and abstract, 573 short communications, letters to editors, proceedings, 336 background articles in non-indexed journals, 39 excluded without full-text, and 332 articles excluded for non-relevant keywords. Eventually, 120 studies were considered for this review and full-text articles were comprehensively reviewed focusing on PAHs and their biomarkers, availability for biological uptake, methods of extraction and quantification, the limits of detection, and mechanisms underlying respiratory toxicity (Table 2). In the course of this review, different PAHs and their exposure effect on the respiratory system were studied including the respective mechanism of their actions on the biological system (figure 1).

The chemical structure of priority PAHs was designed by ACD ChemSketch, USA ver. 2020.2.1. The name, abbreviation, and CAS number were collected from PubChem.

PAHs metabolites detection

PAHs emitted into ambient air are categorized as International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) Group 2A and 2B human carcinogens (Table 1).[43] Detection of PAHs metabolites in biological samples including mucus, urine, blood, plasma, serum, sputum, seminal plasma, and milk *etc.* are critical in assessing human exposure and understanding their potential health effects.[44] PAHs metabolites are formed in the body through metabolic processes following exposure to PAHs, and their presence in biological samples serves as biomarkers of exposure.[45] The detection of PAHs metabolites in environmental samples (water, air and dust) assists in assessing the presence and distribution of contaminants in the environment. In recent years, the detection of PAHs and their metabolites in both biological as well as environmental samples includes more precise and selective analytical techniques such as GCMS or LCMS with more sensitive tools *i.e.* ultraviolet-fluorescence detector mass spectroscopy, HPLC-MSMS negative electrospray ionization, isotope-dilution liquid chromatography with tandem mass spectrometry (ID-LC-MSMS), UPLC Orbitrap MS analysis, *etc.* (Table 2, Table 3).

Biological monitoring

Urine analysis for evaluation of metabolic health, exposure to toxins, drugs, and pathogens is the most preferred method due to non-invasive sample collection procedures, minimal matrix contamination, and wide range of half-life (5 h to 17 days).[27, 46] Both high-performance liquid chromatography-ultraviolet-fluorescence detector mass spectroscopy (HPLC-UV-FLDMS) and gas chromatography-mass spectroscopy (GCMS) techniques are frequently used for urinary PAHs metabolite estimation owing to optimal sensitivity and selectivity.[47] Samples are treated with β -glucuronidase/arylsulfatase enzyme-conjugate for PAHs separation and are further extracted using solid/liquid-liquid extraction (SLE/LLE) and cleanup technique.[48] The extracted PAHs samples are further concentrated, reconstituted in suitable solvents, and quantified (Table 2).

Various studies focused on assessing exposure to PAHs and their metabolites. These studies collectively provide insights into the methodologies, health effects including potential implications for maternal and fetal health, PAHs effect by transfer from mothers to infants through breastfeeding, health effects among workers in high-risk industries, and providing valuable insights into potential environmental factors contributing to respiratory health issues.

Thangphatthanarungruang *et al.* (2023) utilized gas chromatography mass spectrometry to quantify 10 urinary carboxylic acid metabolites, while also employing a graphene poly(L-GA)/SPGE for 1-hydroxypyrene (1-OHP) detection.[49] Zhu *et al.* (2022) evaluated urinary PAHs and their metabolites in pregnant women using HPLC-MS/MS.[50] Shamsedini *et al.* (2022) measured five urinary PAHs metabolites using GCMS.[51] Aung *et al.* (2021) employed an ID-LC-MS/MS method to analyze urinary PAHs metabolites in a single-pollutant model.[52] Fernández *et al.* (2021) conducted biomonitoring of PAHs metabolites in lactating subjects using HPLCMS.[53] Salami *et al.* (2021) correlated PAHs exposure with socio-demographic factors and PM_{2.5} levels in gestating women, analyzing urinary PAHs metabolites via GCMS.[54] Díaz de León-Martínez *et al.* (2021) quantified urinary PAHs metabolites in high-risk occupational groups using GCMS.[55] Shahsavani *et al.* (2022) evaluated PAHs exposure and its association with health outcomes in the population of Shiraz province, Iran, using both blood and urine samples.[56] Hu *et al.* (2022) analyzed urinary 1-OHP in children at high risk of asthma using UPLC Orbitrap MS.[57] Liu *et al.* (2023) studied the effect of PAHs exposure on lung epithelium in coke plant workers, assessing PAHs and nicotine biomarkers in urine and lung epithelium damage biomarker (CC₁₆) in plasma samples.[58]

Environmental monitoring

PAHs bound to PM_{2.5} are considered toxic and prone to mutagenic, carcinogenic, and teratogenic effects.[10, 59–62] In ambient air, multi-ring PAHs were more adsorbed with PM_{2.5} (66%–86%) than PM₁₀ while low-ring PAHs were more accumulated on the PM₁₀ surface (83%–86%).[63] Incomplete biomass combustion during food grilling is the most common cause of PAHs exposure through inhalation of fumes or consumption of grilled food.[64, 65] The highest concentration of PAHs was detected in charcoal-grilled food (382.02 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) while the lowest concentration was observed in gas-grilled food (1.44 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$).[65] Coal grilling activity generated mostly 4-ring PAHs in which coal ash was found abundant in FLU and PYR PAHs.[66] A significant increase in NAP, ACE, FLA, PHE, PYR, and B[a]P was found in urine samples taken while grilling was taking place hours.[67] Three-year average air monitoring in Dalian, North China revealed the presence of 53 PAH compounds in gas and particulate phases, ranging from 40 to 240 ng/m^3 (with an average of $95 \pm 40 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$). This included 26 alkylated PAHs (averaging $17 \pm 7.6 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$), 16 priority PAHs (averaging $68 \pm 33 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$), and 4 high-molecular-weight PAHs (averaging $1.3 \pm 1.3 \text{ ng}/\text{m}^3$). A city-based population attributable fraction due to ambient PAHs exposure was observed at 12.0% and 35.7/million people were attributed to cancer cases due to

excess PAHs inhalation, over a 70-year average lifespan.[68] A total number of 12 PAHs as well as their representative metabolites were analyzed in 170 ambient air samples collected from Chinese cities producing coal and oil and were compared to their respective ILCR. The initial ILCR during the heating season (April-October) was reported as 2.65×10^{-9} in coal-producing and 4.60×10^{-9} in oil-producing cities. During the non-heating season (November-March), initial ILCR was 1.17×10^{-8} and 3.34×10^{-8} , for coal-producing and oil-producing cities, respectively. For the bioaccessible fraction of PAHs and its metabolites (released in the gastrointestinal tract lumen during digestion), the ILCR was lessened by >80% during both periods.[17] PAHs and their halogenated derivatives are abundant in the air, particularly in aerosolized particles smaller than $PM_{2.5}$. [69, 70] The association between $PM_{2.5}$ and PAHs in the ambient environment was identified as the cause of Inhalation Lifetime Cancer Risk (ILCR) in Bangladesh and Japan. The median ILCR observed was 10^{-3} which was greater than the acceptable risk limit (10^{-4}). In Bangladesh, the concentration of PAHs and xenobiotic PAHs (XPAHs) as well as their respective ILCRs were 1-2 times higher than the concentration in Japan.[71]

Mechanism of Action of PAHs Toxicity

Ma *et al.* (2020) reported PHE exposure in association with increased hepatic-pulmonary superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity, malondialdehyde (MDA) content, and 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine (8-OHdG) suggestive of induced oxidative stress in lung and liver of the female rat.[61] Increased IL-6 level was observed after exposure to cooking smoke in a healthy subject. *In vitro* B[a]P exposure (0.2 -2 mM concentration) to microglial cells increased TNF- α , an activator of the classical signalling pathway for transcription factor NF κ B and IL-6, resulting in NF- κ B-derived inflammation and oxidative stress. The protein-mRNA expressions of TNF- α and IL-6 in hepato-pulmonary tissues were increased in human alveolar epithelial cells (A549) following smoke-mediated PHE exposure (Niu *et al.*, 2021).[72] Environmental as well as dietary B[a]P exposure was also found to be in association with pulmonary incremental-lifetime-cancer-risk (ILCR).[24, 73] Industrial trade-driven B[a]P emission was reported to be linked with increased lung cancer incidences.[74]

Exposure to PAHs, toxicity mechanism, and effect on pathophysiology using different experimental models is presented in Table 1. The mechanism of action of PAHs exposure involves (a) absorption in the body through inhalation, ingestion, and dermal contact and distribution in the body via the bloodstream (b) biotransformation to water-soluble metabolites by oxidation, hydroxylation, epoxidation, and conjugation reaction (c) metabolic activation to form reactive intermediates, such as epoxides and quinones that interact and damage DNA, RNA, lipids, protein and enzymes (d) oxidative stress (e) inflammatory responses by activation of immune cells and the release of pro-inflammatory mediators, such as cytokines and chemokines. Recent studies indicate that many signalling pathways are implicated in PAHs-mediated respiratory toxicity.

Priority PAHs adsorbed on $PM_{2.5}$ were found to be in association with increased ROS production, leading to damage to biological macromolecules and lung epithelium. The presence of PAHs adsorbed onto $PM_{2.5}$ can indeed pose greater health risks compared to PAHs in their gaseous or unbound form. When PAHs are adsorbed onto $PM_{2.5}$, both penetrate in lungs more efficiently than gaseous PAHs, increasing the deposition in the respiratory tract. PAHs- $PM_{2.5}$ have a longer residence time in the air compared to gaseous PAHs. $PM_{2.5}$ provides a large surface area to carry a significant number of PAHs leading to higher concentrations in air and subsequently higher exposure levels for individuals. The combination of PAHs with other toxic components present in $PM_{2.5}$, such as heavy metals and VOCs, can result in respiratory system damage.[75-79] The damage induces lipid peroxidation affecting ACTA2 gene expression (regulated by TGF- β inhibitor) and resulting in altered cellular functioning.[21, 23] The detectable concentration of PAHs in human breast milk especially dibenz[a,h]anthracene (DB[ah]A) caused growth retardation, neurobehavioral changes in infants, and increased chances of allergies and respiratory diseases.[80] The cytotoxic effect of DB[ah]A combined with $PM_{2.5}$ led to oxidative stress-mediated cell membrane damage and inflammatory response in A549 cells.[81] Tseng *et al.* (2021) reported B[a]P exposure and associated respiratory health problems.[82] It was concluded that both aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AhR) antagonist as well as transforming growth factor β (TGF- β) signalling pathways caused a decline in collagen type I -COL1, actin α 2 -ACTA2, and E-cadherin gene expression).[83, 84] On the contrary, non-expression of the podoplanin (PDPN) and its marker genes following B[a]P exposure was detected. Arsenic and B[a]P co-exposure in human bronchial epithelial BEAS-2B cells resulted in bronchial cancerous stem cell-like behaviour by activating the hedgehog pathway and up-regulation of integrin- α . [85] B[a]P-induced human lung carcinoma and induction of p21-dependent epithelial-mesenchymal transition-like phenotype was observed in human carcinoma alveolar basal epithelial cells, type II (A549 cells) by Hýžd'álová *et al.* (2021).[86] Exposure to B[a]P resulted in the upregulation of human genes associated with AhR metabolism and nuclear translocation, heat shock protein (HSP₉₀), and CYP1A1. B[a]P exposure caused an increase in the expression of AhR gene as well as caused the activation of pathways

associated with Epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) (Nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor2 -NRF2, Kirsten ras oncogene -KRAS, and hypoxia-inducible factor 1 α), mesenchymal phenotype markers, N-cadherin, fibronectin, and vimentin. In contrast, B[a]P exposure caused down-regulation of E-cadherin gene expression.[87, 88] B[a]P-induced injury in human alveolar epithelial cell line A549 was observed with a decline in fibrotic mass, and G-protein-coupled receptor class C group 5 member A (Gprc5a).[89] Effect of 2-Benz[j]aceanthrylene was observed in human hepatocellular carcinoma cells by DNA damage signal activation which was indicated by sensitive markers pChk1 and γ H2A histone family member X (γ H2AX).[90] The relationship between high-molecular-weight PAH, fluorene and DNA methylation causing cancer was evidenced by Xu *et al.* (2024).[91] The fluorene exposure was associated with lower DNA methylation of *F2RL3* and *AHRR*, epigenetic biomarkers for lung cancer.

Guo *et al.* (2020) and Da Silva Junior *et al.* (2021) even observed the genotoxicity of 2-Benz[j]aceanthrylene to in turn cause DNA damage using DNA adduct formation (Figure 1).[17, 92, 93] The association between PAHs and hepatic physiology was observed by Xu *et al.* (2021) in 3194 subjects.[93] Female subjects showed an increase in serum alanine transaminase (ALT) levels following 2-FLU exposure (OR = 2.33, CI (95%) 1.15, 4.72). Urinary 2-FLU exposure (38.6%) was responsible for increased ALT concentration (OR = 2.19 CI 95% 1.12, 4.27, $p = 0.004$). 2-Fluorene exposure was associated with leukocytosis (3.56%), hypertriglyceridemia (6.99%), and hypercholesterolemia (1.70%) than normal.[94]

Impaired pulmonary redox, inflammation, immunosuppression, and pulmonary malignancy were observed in mice with increased expression of nuclear factor- κ B (NF κ B), cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2), inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS); tumor necrosis factor α (TNF- α), proliferating cell nuclear antigen (PCNA), and matrix remodelling enzymes in mice.[95] B[a]P exposure induced the AhR activation which induced allergic airway inflammation.[94]

DISCUSSION

Exposure to PAHs, whether outdoors or indoors, has been associated with increased health problems including endocrine cancers, developmental toxicity, cardiovascular and pulmonary toxicity, lower plasma insulin-like growth factor-1, reduced immune function, and more.[96, 97] This broad spectrum of adverse effects underscores the significant toxicological concerns associated with PAHs, sparking heightened interest in understanding, and addressing their impact.[34, 82, 98–103] PAHs exposure is also linked with respiratory problems including allergy, asthma, COPD, emphysema, and lung cancer.[58, 104, 105] PAHs exposure occurs mostly through food uptake and/or inspiration.[106] For non-smokers, the main exposure source is combusted food (charcoal-broiled food) while for smokers, smoking is a significant source of exposure. PAHs absorption in the human body occur via respiratory, gastrointestinal, or dermal routes each of which involves different routes and metabolic pathways. These processes encompass the formation of DNA adducts, DNA lesions, alterations in cell cycle regulation, activation of the AhR receptor leading to toxicity, genotoxicity mediated by reactive oxygen species (ROS) and oxidative stress, modulation of protein expression, and disruption of lipid metabolism.[107–109] PAHs oxidation-conjugation in phase I and II induces phase I (cytochrome P450 monooxygenases – CYP1A1/2 and 1B1) as well as phase II metabolic enzymes (aldo-keto reductases, epoxide hydrolases, glutathione S-transferases, nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADP) quinone oxidoreductases, and uridine 5'-diphospho-glucuronosyltransferase) via AhR-dependent and AhR-independent pathways (Figure 1). AKR, CYP peroxidase, and CYP1A1/1B1/EH pathway mediated PAHs metabolism form reactive metabolites *i.e.*, carcinogenic diol-epoxides, radical cations, and *o*-quinones to produce DNA adduct causing mutations, altered gene expression, and oncogenesis. The mutation in the xenobiotic metabolic and p53 genes is related to increased susceptibility to lung cancer.[110, 111] Exposure *via* the intratracheal route significantly affects hepatic fatty acid metabolism as well as alters glycerolipids, glycerophospholipids, triacylglycerol, phosphatidylinositol, phosphatidylcholine levels with decreased concentrations of lysophosphatidylcholine, phosphatidylethanolamine, lysophosphatidylethanolamine, free fatty acids, and eicosanoids.[5, 112]

CONCLUSION

PAHs have been classified based on human toxicity, most of which are associated with inhalation, ingestion, and dermal contact. Scientific evidence of recently published literature points out the emerging contribution of exposure to polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and their respiratory effects. The presence of PAHs adsorbed to particulate matter, specifically PM_{2.5}, can contribute to increased health risks than PAHs alone. This can be attributed to the size-specific penetration efficacy of PM_{2.5} due to enhanced inhalation and deposition, extended residence time, and synergistic health effects, by serving as PAHs transportation carrier which

enables it to reach alveolar cells more efficiently than PM (size $>5 \mu$). This review finds that PAHs exposure causes health ailments involving AhR-mediated interlinked signalling pathways which result in increased oxidative stress, immune system damage, asthma/COPD, and cancer. Reduction in ambient air pollution can significantly improve human health globally. The present review concluded a comprehensive and robust approach for the respiratory toxicity evaluation of PAHs and their biologically active metabolites. The findings of this review may serve as a baseline approach for designing future research studies and establishing policy implications related to the toxicity of PAHs. More studies are needed to relate, clarify, support, and strengthen the role of PAHs particularly with multiple-pollutant exposure or in multidisciplinary studies including PAHs respiratory toxicity. By undertaking these research activities, studies can contribute to a better understanding of the role of PAHs in respiratory toxicity and inform evidence-based strategies for mitigating the associated health risks.

FUTURE RESEARCH, PRACTICE, AND POLICY IMPLICATION

Future research needs more focus on understanding the mechanisms including specific pathways underlying PAHs-induced respiratory toxicity including inflammation, oxidative stress, and DNA damage, identifying biomarkers of early biological effects, susceptibility, development of longitudinal studies to assess the long-term respiratory health outcomes, and evaluating intervention strategies. Practice should involve occupational health measures for comprehensive risk assessment and management, training, and education programs to increase awareness of PAHs hazards, development and enforcement of environmental regulations, and clinical care improvements. Policy recommendations include strengthening regulatory frameworks, promoting intersectoral collaboration, and raising public awareness.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

R.G. & M.M. conceptualized the study and performed literature survey, methodology, investigation, writing of review, and visualization. S.Y., P.K.A & S.P. performed supervision, visualization, validation, and editing.

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The present research did not receive any financial support.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is not any conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/ or falsification, double publication and/or submission, and redundancy has been completely observed by the authors.

LIFE SCIENCE REPORTING

No life science threat was practiced in this research.

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Table 1. PAHs exposure, toxicity mechanism, and molecular effect.

PAHs	Study model	Objective	Parameters	Exposure Effects	Mechanism of toxicity	References
IARC Monographs Group 1	Bronchial epithelial cell-line (BEAS-2B cells), nude mice	As and B[a]P co-exposure in the induction of tumorigenesis	Western blot analysis, Soft-agar colony development assay, Serum-free suspension culture, sphere formation assay, ALDEFLUOR assay, chromatin immunoprecipitation (ChIP)-q-PCR, Benzo [a]pyrene diol epoxide (BPDE)-DNA adduct level analysis, hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) and Immunofluorescence, Immunohistochemistry	Malignancy of immortal non-tumorigenic bronchial epithelium cells, cancer stem cell, and lung adenomas	Activation of AhR pathway; upregulation of H3K9 methyltransferase, suppressor of variegation 3-9 homolog1 (SUV39H1) expression and suppressive H3K9 dimethylation (H3K9me2); downregulation of tumor suppression suppressor of cytokine signalling 3 (SOCS3) expression; activation of Akt and Extracellular signal-regulated kinases (Erk1/2); increased cell transformation, CSC-like property, and tumorigenesis	[83]
<i>Human Carcinogen (126 agents)</i> B[a]P	BEAS-2B cells	B[a]P exposure induced lung epithelial cell signalling	Transwell assay, Cell viability assay, Immunofluorescence	Increased BEAS-2B cell invasion, migration	Increase in expression of B[a]P metabolism-related mRNA and protein (AhR and target genes <i>i.e.</i> nuclear translocator, HSP90, and CYP1A1); increased mRNA expression of AhR signal pathway, EMT (NRF2, K-RAS, and hypoxia-inducible factor 1-alpha) like downstream regulatory factors; down-regulation of epithelium marker E-cadherin expression; upregulation of mesenchymal phenotype markers, N-cadherin, fibronectin and vimentin mRNA expression	[87]

Human hepatocellular carcinoma cells (HepG2) cells	Synergistic effects of B[a]P and pesticides <i>i.e.</i> chlorpyrifos, paraquat and tebuconazole on human HepG2 cell, AhR signalling	Exposure of HepG2 cell to B[a]P, Cell viability assay by inhibitory concentration (IC ₅₀), Quantitative real-time PCR, CYP1A1 enzyme inhibition assay, Intracellular ROS assay, In cell western (ICW) assay, AhR knockdown, Assessment of morphological effects, mortality and GFP expression in zebrafish, analysis for cytotoxicity endpoint	B[a]P and paraquat/tebuconazole caused additive effects on cell viability, mixture with chlorpyrifos - antagonistic effect on cell viability and ROS production, developmental toxicity of bladder, yolk sac and pericardial edema, and spinal deformation in zebrafish	B[a]P and paraquat/tebuconazole-additive effects on <i>CYP1A1</i> expression, mixture with chlorpyrifos-induction of <i>CYP1A1</i> expression, inhibition of recombinant human <i>CYP1A1</i> enzyme activity, synergistic expression induction of <i>CYP1A</i>	[113]
CD54 ⁺ CD157 ⁺ CD45 ⁻ cells mice lung stem cells	B[a]P induced fibrotic changes in lung stem cells	Cell cultures, Proliferation and viability assays, qRT-PCR, SDS-PAGE and immunoblot analysis, cell image analysis, Antibody testing	Increased fibrosis, repressed 3D spheroid formation, α -1,6-fucosylation loss by non-canonical aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AhR) signalling pathway, decreased cell growth in CD54 ⁺ CD157 ⁺ CD45 ⁻ cells; impaired lung stem cell regeneration	B[a]P exposure promoted AhR nuclear translocation; impaired TGF- β signalling, non-expression of podoplanin marker of alveolar differentiation; reduced COL1 and ACTA2 expression; repression of PDPN expression and spheroid formation; suppressed of E-cadherin expression	[82]
Human bronchial epithelial BEAS-2B cell, Nude mouse	Arsenic and B[a]P co-exposure and bronchial cancerous stem cell-like behavior, tumorigenesis mechanism	Microarray analysis, Integrin subunit α 4 (ITGA4) stable knockdown model, suppressor of fused (SUFU) stable overexpression cells, Soft-agar colony formation assay, Serum-free suspension culture sphere formation assay,		Activation of hedgehog pathway by up-regulation of Integrin α 4 evaluated cancerous stem cell-like property and tumorigenesis	[85]

			Quantitative PCR analysis, immunohistochemistry			
Human lung carcinoma (A549) cells	Prolonged B[a]P exposure and progression of human lung carcinoma, and induction of p21 dependent epithelial-mesenchymal transition like phenotype	Transcriptomic analysis	Induction of epithelial-mesenchymal transition phenotype by decreased cell proliferation	-		[86]
BEAS-2B, A549 cell line, Human eosinophilic leukemia cell line (EOL-1), BALB/cAnN Mice	B[a]P induced AhR activation increases in allergic airway inflammation	Cell line culture, Fluorescence-Activated Cell Sorting	Increased lung inflammation and eosinophil infiltration	AhR activation and airway inflammation significantly increased IL-33 expression; increased IL-8 expression in EOL-1 (house dust mite-activated), BEAS-2B, and A549 cells; increased IL-33 in BEAS-2B cells		[94]
C57BL/6 mice, clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats (CRISPR)/Cas9 knockout Gprc5a ^{-/-} mice, A549 cell line	B[a]P induced injury in human alveolar basal epithelial A549 cell line	Histology, Transmission electron microscopy, Western blotting, Sircol assay, immunohistochemistry, immunofluorescence, bioinformatics analysis	Dense and damaged alveolar type II cell membrane, decline in fibrotic mass, Gprc5a depletion worsen mortality rate with high collagen accumulation and myofibroblast activation, idiopathic interstitial pneumonia	Increase in bleomycin-induced murine pulmonary fibrosis as well as fibronectin and α smooth muscle actin (α SMA) expression in primary fibroblasts; decreased GPRC5A mRNA expression; Opa1-regulated mitochondrial dynamics or Mitofusion2 and vitamin metabolic imbalance were responsible for decreased Gprc5a and fibrogenesis		[89]

	Human BEAS-2B and A549 cell	Combination of low molecular weight PAHs and B[a]P as co-carcinogen	Micronucleus assay of BEAS-2B and C ₁₀ cell, cell cycle analysis, scalpel-loaded dye transfer assay, DNA adducts and immunoblots, DNA extraction and quantitation, analysis of anti-BPDE-DNA adducts, CYP1B1 immunoblots of BEAS-2B and A549 cells	-	After PAHs and B[a]P treatment micronuclei formation increased, gap junctional intercellular communication regulation altered, cell cycle alteration, increased anti-BPDE-DNA adducts	[114]
	Mice	Induction of epithelial injury by B[a]P	Lung histopathology, CC ₁₆ Immunohistochemistry analysis, Immunofluorescence staining, RNA extraction and qRT-PCR, Western blot	Increased lung inflammatory response and dose dependent decrease in Clara cell secretory protein (CC ₁₆) expression	Lung inflammation and airway epithelial injury, activation of non-canonical Wnt5a-YAP/TAZ signalling by Wnt5a	[98]
	Mice	Pulmonary redox damage, inflammation, and immunosuppressed IL-27 and IL-28B in B[a]P induced lung cancer	Histology, biochemistry, immunohistochemistry, Western blot, cytotoxicity assay, real time PCR	Pulmonary redox damage, inflammation, immunosuppression	Expression increased in Pulmonary malignancy-associated NFkB, COX-2, iNOS; TNF-α, PCNA, and matrix remodeling enzymes	[95]
	Rats	Lung cancer risk assessment	-	Lung cancer	Modulates Nrf2/Keap1 axis, upregulation of activating transcription factor-6, C/EBP Homologous Protein; induction of endoplasmic reticulum stress	[115]
IARC Monographs Group 2A <i>Probably carcinogenic to humans (94 agents)</i>	¹ Human hepatocellular carcinoma cells (HepG2)	PAHs and PM in indoor dust, and genotoxic potential	Ambient and indoor PM ₁₀ ; analysis of PAHs and OPAHs; measurement of ROS by pChk1 and γH2AX (sensitive markers DNA damage); western blotting	Carcinogenic and genotoxic effect	DNA damage by pChk1 and γH2AX signalling	[90]

Cyclopenta[c, d]pyrene CPP; Dibenzo[a,l]p yrene; DB[a,l]P ¹ ; Dibenz[a,h]ant hracene DB[a,h]A ²	Human BEAS-2B and A549 cell	Combination of low molecular weight PAHs and B[a]P as co- carcinogen	Micronucleus assay of BEAS-2B and C ₁₀ cell, cell cycle analysis, scalpel-loaded dye transfer assay, DNA adducts and immunoblots, DNA extraction and quantitation, analysis of anti-BPDE-DNA adducts, CYP1B1 immunoblots of BEAS- 2B and A549 cells	-	After PAHs and B[a]P treatment micronuclei formation increased, gap junctional intercellular communication regulatio n altered, cell cycle alteration, increased anti- BPDE-DNA adducts	[114]
	² Human breast milk in nursing mothers	PAHs exposure effect in nursing mothers and infants'	PAHs (un-metabolized and metabolized) extraction from milk; chromatographic analysis	Growth retardation; neurobehavioral changes in child; increased chances of allergies and respiratory diseases	-	[80]
	Human A549 cells	Sub-toxic effects of engine emissions and truck speed	Air sampling vehicle exhaust, determination of ionic content, PAHs quantitation, analysis of A549 cell culture, exposure and viability, Real-time PCR analysis of exposed A549 cell line, exhaust extract/EGCG exposure	Phenanthrene was abundant in vehicle emission, HMW PAHs were emitted at high speed (>50%) <i>i.e.</i> B[ghi], Indeno[1,2,3- cd]pyrene (I[cd]P)	Induction of IL-6, CYP1A1, and NQO-1	[116]
	-	Environment al toxicity and health effects	-	COPD, ALRI, ischemic heart disease, stroke, and cataracts	ROS induction effects	[117]
	² A549 cells	Cytotoxic effect of PM _{2.5} by vehicular emission	Mass concentrations of PM _{2.5} ; cell culture for cytokines determination	Oxidative and inflammatory effect	Oxidative stress- mediated cell membrane damage; inflammatory effect in A549 cells characterized by lactate dehydrogenase (LDH), 8- <i>iso</i> -PGF2 α and IL-6	[118]
	² Human epidemiolo gical study	Environment al PAHs exposure and altered respiratory	Association of PM _{2.5} with bound 16 PAHs; urinary 8-OHdG and 8- isoprostane (8- <i>iso</i> - PGF2 α) analysis	Impaired lung function; decrease in forced expiratory volume	Increased ROS degrade biological macromolecules and cause lung epithelium impairment; lipid	[21]

		function and mechanism			peroxidation of cell membrane; altered ACTA2 by TGF-β inhibitor SB431542	
<p>IARC Monographs Group 2B</p> <p><i>Possibly carcinogenic to humans (322 agents)</i></p> <p>Benz[<i>j</i>]aceanthrylene³; benzo[<i>a</i>]anthracene⁴; benzo[<i>b</i>]fluoranthene; benzo[<i>j</i>]fluoranthene; benzo[<i>k</i>]fluoranthene; benzo[<i>c</i>]phenanthrene; chrysene; dibenzo[<i>a,h</i>]pyrene; dibenzo[<i>a,i</i>]pyrene; indeno[1,2,3-<i>cd</i>]pyrene; 5-methylchrysene</p>	³ Human hepatocellular carcinoma cells (HepG2)	2-and 3-Nitrobenzanthrone exposure in urban air and oxidative stress, DNA adduct formation	Indoor and outdoor PM ₁₀ , dust sampling, chemical analysis of PAH and OHPAHs, Cell culture and exposure, Measurements of ROS, western blotting	Geno-toxicity in both human lung A549 and liver HepG2 cells	DNA damage signal activation through pChk1 and γH2AX are sensitive markers	[90]
	Human A549 cells	Sub-toxic effects of engine emissions and truck speed	Air sampling vehicle exhaust, determination of ionic content, PAHs quantitation, analysis of A549 cell culture, exposure and viability, Real-time PCR analysis of exposed A549 cell line, exhaust extract/EGCG exposure	HMW PAHs were emitted at high speed (>50%) <i>i.e.</i> B[ghi], I[cd]P)	Induction of IL-6, CYP1A1, and NQO-1	[116]
	³ A549 cells	Cytotoxic effect of PM _{2.5} by vehicular emission	Mass concentrations of PM _{2.5} ; cell culture for cytokines determination	Oxidative and inflammatory effect	Oxidative stress-mediated cell membrane damage; inflammatory effect in A549 cells characterized by LDH, 8- <i>iso</i> -PGF2α, and IL-6	[118]
	⁴ Human milk	PAHs exposure effect in nursing mothers and infants	PAHs (un-metabolized and metabolized) extraction from milk; chromatographic analysis	Growth retardation; neurobehavioral changes in child; increased chances of allergies and respiratory diseases	-	[80]
	-	PM-bound PAHs and health risk	PAHs analysis and toxicity determination; inhalation carcinogenic risk assessment	Carcinogenic risk	-	[119]

IARC Monographs Group 3 <i>Not classifiable as to its carcinogenicity to humans⁴ (500 agents)</i>	Human A549 cells	Sub-toxic effects of engine emissions and truck speed	Air sampling vehicle exhaust, determination of ionic content, PAHs quantitation, analysis of A549 cell culture, exposure and viability, Real-time PCR analysis of exposed A549 cell line, exhaust extract/EGCG exposure	Phenanthrene was abundant in vehicle emission, HMW PAHs were emitted at high speed (>50%) i.e. B[ghi], I[cd]P)	Induction of IL-6, CYP1A1, and NQO-1	[116]
	-	PM-bound PAHs and health risk	PAHs analysis and toxicity determination; inhalation carcinogenic risk assessment	Carcinogenic risk	-	[119]

Not classifiable as to its carcinogenicity to humans⁴: Acenaphthene (ACE); acepyrene; (3,4-dihydrocyclopenta[cd]pyrene); anthracene⁴; 1H-benz[bc]aceanthrylene; benz[l]aceanthrylene; benzo[b]chrysene; benzo[g]chrysene; benzo[a]fluoranthene; benzo[ghi]fluoranthene; benzo[a]fluorene; benzo[b]fluorene; benzo[c]fluorene; benzo[ghi]perylene; benzo[e]pyrene; coronene; 4H-cyclopenta[def]chrysene; 5,6-cyclopenteno-1,2-benzanthracene; dibenz[a,c]anthracene; dibenz[a,j]anthracene; dibenzo[a,e]fluoranthene; 13H-dibenzo[a,g]fluorene; dibenzo[h,rst]pentaphene; dibenzo[a,e]pyrene; dibenzo[e,l]pyrene³; 1,2-dihydroaceanthrylene, 1,4-dimethylphenanthrene; fluoranthene⁵; fluorene⁵; 1-methylchrysene; 2-methylchrysene; 3-methylchrysene; 4-methylchrysene; 6-methylchrysene; 2-methylfluoranthene; 3-methylfluoranthene; 1-methylphenanthrene; naphtho[1,2-b]fluoranthene; naphtho[2,1-a]fluoranthene; naphtho[2,3-e]pyrene; perylene; phenanthrene; picene; pyrene; triphenylene

Table 2. Quantification of PAHs metabolites.

S. No	Objective	Sample	PAHS detection	Instrum ent	Sample prepara tion	Instrument parameters	Range	Result	Referenc es
1.	Quick, simple, cost-effective, portable, accurate, precise, and reliable test to detect PAHs	Human urine samples	1-hydroxypyrene	GCMS	Graphene poly(L-GA)/SPGE based on poly(l-glutamic acid)	Electrochemical device based on poly(l-glutamic acid)-modified a screen-printed graphene electrode (poly(L-GA)/SPGE)	Linearity 1-1000 nm; LOQ 3.16 nm; LOD 0.95 nm	Early detection of illness risk using developed sensor	[49]
2.	Correlation between their metabolite concentrations, socioeconomic, demographic	Urine of pregnant women during second and	1-hydroxypyrene glucuronide	HPLC-MS/MS: C18 column and gradient elution using negative	1.0 ml ethyl acetate (5 mmol/L	Voltage -2500 V, sheath gas pressure – 35, auxiliary gas pressure – 10, and ion sweep N ₂ gas pressure – 2.0 au, capillary, vaporizer	Detection rate over 74%	Pregnant women have a greater 1-OHPG concentration due to unhealthy diet and increased indoor exposure	[22]

	c, and dietary factors	third trimester		electrospray ionization mode		temperature – 350 °C)			
3.	Health risk assessment of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in individuals living near restaurants	Urine and serum samples	Metabolites of 1-Naphthalene, 2-Naphthalene, 2-Fluorene, 1-Hydroxypyrene, and 9-Phenanthrene	GCMS with HP5-MS capillary column	Hydrolysis by β -glucuronidase/arylsulfatase	-	-	Highest concentration found at 1-OHP level. No significant difference between Σ OH-PAHs levels	[51]
4.	Estimation of endogenous biomarker associations with prenatal phenols, phthalates, metals, and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in single-pollutant and mixtures analysis approaches	Urine sample of participants <15 weeks gestation and age >18 years	1-naphthalene, 2-naphthalene, 2-fluorene, 1-phenanthrene, 2-phenanthrene, 3-phenanthrene, 4-phenanthrene, 9-phenanthrene, 1-pyrene	ID-LC-MSMS, HPLC-ESI-MS/MS	-	-	-	Four PAH metabolites (2-FLU, 2- and 3-PHE, 1-PHE, and 1-PYR) were positively associated with the oxidative stress marker 8-IP	[52]
5.	Biomonitoring of PAHs metabolites	Urine of lactating subjects	1-hydroxynaphthalene, 2-hydroxynaphthalene, 2-hydroxyfluorene, 1-hydroxyphenanthrene, 1-hydroxyphenanthrene, 3-	HPLCMS water/methanol (40:60) containing 0.1% of acetic acid			LOQ- 0.05 ng/ml for 3OHFLU and 3OHBAP, and 0.01 ng/ml for rest of OHPAHs	Estimated daily intake - naphthalene, fluorene, phenanthrene, and pyrene- 6 to 1522 ng /kg/day;	[53]

			hydroxyphenanthrene, 4-hydroxyphenanthrene, and 3-hydroxybenzo(a)pyrene, 3-Hydroxyfluorene, 9-hydroxyphenanthrene, and 1-hydroxypyrene						
6.	PAHs exposure with socio-demographic factors and PM _{2.5} exposure	Non-smoking pregnant women (first and third trimester)	1-naphthol, 2-naphthol, 9-phenanthrene, and 1-hydroxypyrene	GCMSMS	-	-	-	Urban residents were exposed to higher level of PAHs especially in the cold season	[54]
7.	Urinary metabolites of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in precarious workers of highly exposed occupational group	High-risk occupational groups (brick makers, stone masons, and mercury miners)	1-hydroxynaphthalene and 2-hydroxynaphthalene; 2-,3- and 9-hydroxyfluorene; 1-,2-,3- and 4-hydroxyphenanthrene; and 1-hydroxypyrene	GCMS electron impact ionization mode, HP 5MS column	β-glucuronidase/arylsulfatase, acetate buffer (1 M, pH 5.5)	splitless mode, temperature 270 °C; helium as carrier gas pressure 36 psi with constant flow 0.9 mL/ml	-	PAHs concentrations were similar in some metabolites higher than workers in occupations classified as carcinogenic by the IARC	[55]

8.	Relationship between urinary metabolite of PAH (OH-PAHs) level and the oxidative stress biomarker (Malondialdehyde)	Urine of healthy subject	1-HydroxyPyrene, 2-HydroxyNaphthalene, 2-HydroxyFluorene	-	-	-	-	PAHs exposure-mediated hazard quotient was found between 0.009 to 14.92 for FLU, and 0.005 to 8.43 for NAP in sex-dependent non-cancer problems	[56]
9.	To explore PAHs exposure in childhood asthma by metabolic profiles	Urine of children with asthma and 30 children as control	1-hydroxypyrene	UPLC-Orbitrap-MS	0.2 M sodium acetate (pH = 5) and β glucuronidase with sulfatase extracted by dichloromethane	Hypersil Gold C18 column (1.9 μ m, 2.1 \times 100 mm) and analyzed by linear gradient elution, mobile phase methanol and ultrapure water	LOD 0.1 ng/mL	Urinary 1-OHPyr exposure was associated with childhood asthma, microbial diversity, and metabolic profiles	[57]
10.	PAHs exposure effect on lung epithelium	Coke plant workers	Club cell secretory protein	HPLC-FD-MS	Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay	-	-	CC16 association with PAH and tobacco smoke exposure and reduced lung function.	[58]

Table 3. Detection limit and concentration of Priority PAHs.

S. No.	Name/Abbreviation/CAS #	Structure (M.W.)	Detection limit	Concentration/recovery	Reference
1.	Acenaphthene ACE (83-32-9)	 (154.21)	0.01-0.05 μ g/kg	1.78-11.19 μ g/kg	[120]
			5 pg μ l	82 \pm 15% with ~10 ng	[121]
				0.003 \pm 0.002 ng/m ³ in PM _{2.5}	[122]
			0.017	0.03- 0.83 μ g/mg	[1088]
2.	Acenaphthylene ACY (208-96-8)	 (152.19)	0.01-0.06 μ g/kg	23.20- 180.77 μ g/kg	[121]
			-	0.020 \pm 0.010 ng/m ³ in PM _{2.5}	[122]
			0.010	ND to 1.05 μ g/mg	[123]
			<10%	-	[1088]
3.	Anthracene ANT		0.01-0.02 μ g/kg	7.27- 157.50 μ g/kg	[122]
			0.013	0.02- 1.21 μ g/mg	[121]

	(120-12-7)	 (178.23)	-	0.030±0.020 ng/m ³ in PM _{2.5}	[1088]
4.	Benz[a]anthracene B[a]A (56-55-3)	 (228.29)	9.1 pg/ml	0.06±0.01 ^S ; 0.51±0.29 ^W	[122]
			0.01-0.02 µg/kg	ND- 99.97 µg/kg	[121]
			-	0.410±0.460 ng/m ³ in PM _{2.5}	[124]
			0.013	0.02-1.22 µg/mg	[1088]
5.	Benzo[b]fluoranthene B[b]F (205-99-2)	 (253.32)	55.5 pg/ml	0.27±0.04 ^S ; 1.32±0.43 ^W	[122]
			0.01-0.03 µg/kg	ND-89.31 µg/kg	[121]
			0.019	0.01 -1.06 µg/mg	[125]
			-	1.460±1.250 ng/m ³ in PM _{2.5}	[124]
			0.485 µg/g	Carcinogenic potency with respect to Benzo[a]pyrene-toxic equivalent (BaPTEQ) - 0.000-0.049 µg/day	[1088]
6.	Benzo[k]fluoranthene B[k]F (207-08-9)	 (253.32)	8.8 pg/ml	0.07±0.02 ^S ; 0.47±0.16 ^W	[122]
			0.01-0.02 µg/kg	ND- 42.83 µg/kg	[120]
			-	98 ± 7% with ~10 ng 0.600±0.470 ng/m ³ in PM _{2.5}	[121,124] [124]
			0.028	0.01-1.06 µg/mg	[125]
			0.060 µg/g	Carcinogenic potency with respect to BaPTEQ - 0.000- 0.006 µg/day	[1088]
7.	Benzo[a]pyrene B[a]P (50-32-8)	 (253.32)	8.8 pg/ml	0.07±0.02 ^S ; 0.47±0.16 ^W	[120]
			0.01-0.03 µg/kg	ND- 163.31 µg/kg	[121]
			100 fg µ/l	-	[124]
			-	0.970±0.820 ng/m ³ in PM _{2.5}	[125]
			0.066 µg/g	Carcinogenic potency with respect to BaPTEQ - 0.000- 0.066 µg/day	[1088]
8.	Chrysene CHR (218-01-9)	 (228.29)	34.3pg/ml	0.09±0.02 ^S ; 0.83±0.40 ^W	[57]
			0.018	0.56-1.37 µg/mg	[121]
			0.01 µg/kg	ND	[124]
			-	0.630±0.560 ng/m ³ in PM _{2.5}	[125]
			0.020 µg/g	Carcinogenic potency with respect to BaPTEQ - 0.000- 0.002 µg/day	[1088]
9.	Fluoranthene FLA (206-44-0)	 (202.26)	16.2 pg/ml	0.15±0.04 ^S ; 1.39±0.92 ^W	[121]
			0.02-0.04 µg/kg	9.58-122.70 µg/kg	[124]
			-	0.040±0.020 ng/m ³ in PM _{2.5}	[125]
			0.023	0.04-1.00 µg/mg	[122]
			0.483 µg/g	Carcinogenic potency with respect to BaPTEQ - 0.000- 0.048 µg/day	[1088]

10.	Fluorene FLU (86-73-7)	 (166.22)	0.01-0.04 µg/kg	14.43-77.80 µg/kg	[122]
			0.016	0.02-1.02 µg/mg	[125&]
			0.452 µg/g	Carcinogenic potency with respect to BaPTEQ - 0.000- 0.072 µg/day	[1088]
11.	Naphthalene NAP (91-20-3)	 (128.17)	0.02 µg/kg	15.60-87.25 µg/kg	[122]
			0.014	0.01- 1.05 µg/mg	[125&]
			19.440 µg/g	Carcinogenic potency with respect to BaPTEQ - 0.000-0.019µg/day	[1088]
12.	Phenanthrene PHE (85-01-8)	 (178.23)	0.01-0.02 µg/kg	36.81-583.04 µg/kg	[125&]
			0.026 µg/g	ND - 1.00	[122]
			2.726 µg/g	Carcinogenic potency with respect to BaPTEQ - 0.020- 0.047 µg/day	[1088]
13.	Pyrene PYR (129-00-0)	 (202.26)	30.3 pg/ml	0.11±0.01 ^S ; 0.85±0.58 ^W	[122]
			0.02-0.09 µg/kg	9.42-555.14 µg/kg	[120]
			6.7 ng/g	-	[122]
			0.018	0.03-0.83 µg/mg	[124]
			0.1 ng/ml	0.10-1.51 µmol/mol	[125&]
			0.529 µg/g	Carcinogenic potency with respect to BaPTEQ - 0.020- 0.064 µg/day	[1088]
14.	Indeno[1,2,3-cd]pyrene I[cd]P (193-39-5)	 (276.34)	82.9 pg/ml	0.22±0.05 ^S ; 0.80±0.22 ^W	[122]
			0.03-0.06 µg/kg	ND-106.94 µg/kg	[120]
			100 pg/g	Recovery 46 ± 12% with ≤5 ng	[125&]
			0.013	0.01-1.18 µg/mg	[124]
			0.149 µg/g	Carcinogenic potency with respect to BaPTEQ - 0.020- 0.097 µg/day	[1088]
15.	Dibenz[a,h]anthracene DB[ah]A (215-58-7)	 (278.35)	0.02-0.07 µg/kg	ND	[122]
			0.022	ND-0.01 µg/mg	[125&]
			0.064 µg/g	-	[1088]
16.	Benzo[g,h,i]perylene B[ghi]P	 (276.34)	55.3 pg/ml	0.27±0.05 ^S ; 0.98±0.27 ^W	[122]
			0.04-0.07 µg/kg	ND-124.79 µg/kg	[124]
			0.004	ND-1.47 µg/mg	[1088]

^SSummer; ^WWinter; BaPTEQ- B[a]P Toxic Equivalency ⁴Food sample/grilled meat; ND- Not detected

Figure 1. PAHS: Source, Exposure, and signalling mechanism.^{20,28,29}

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